

MONITORING AND SIMULATION OF NON-UNIFORM CURE PROCESS OF FRP BY EMBEDDED SENSORS

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ABSTRACT

In the present paper, we propose a measurement method of degree-of-cure (DOC) distribution of FRP laminates by embedded Fresnel-based fiber-optic refractive-index sensors. The measured data was compared to prediction by thermochemical simulation. A refractive-index sensor can measure cure-index from reflection rate at boundary fiber and resin. Since the sensor diameter is 0.125mm, it can be embedded between prepregs. Twelve sheets of GFRP prepreg were stacked in the same direction on an aluminium flat plate. Three optical fiber sensors were embedded between 1/2 layers, 10/11 layers and 19/20 layers of laminates. In order to apply non-uniform temperature distribution in the thickness-wise direction, the upper plates heated from room temperature up to 140°C in 70 minutes and the lower plate, in 140 minutes. From the experimental results, we could successfully measure DOC curves of the laminates at the three embedding points. The measured DOC curves showed that the thickness-wise distribution of DOC generated during cure process due to inhomogeneous temperature distribution. It appeared that the difference of cure index at each point is large when cure reaction started at the fastest point, however, finally the difference became to zero when cure reaction finished at the slowest point. The thermo-chemical model of cure reaction of the prepreg was obtained by a DSC analysis. From the results of simulation, it was found that the behaviours of DOC curves were similar to the experimental curves.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fast and low-cost manufacturing technologies of large and complex-shaped FRP structures have become developed for consumer applications such as automotive. However, it is difficult to obtain optimized parameters efficiently for molding of such large FRP components because non-uniform distribution of temperature causes inhomogeneous distribution of degree-of-cure (DOC). Therefore, many real-time process monitoring systems using in situ sensors have been developed.

Among sensors for process monitoring, implantable fiber optic sensors are promising to measure DOC of FRP during molding due to thin fiber shape, flexibility, high strength, high functionality and high durability. Many kinds of sensing method using optical fibers embedded in materials have been proposed [1]. Monitoring molding process of polymers, infrared absorption spectrometers [2-5], cure monitoring technique by fiber-optic refractive-index measurement [6-8], and strain measurement techniques using an EFPI (Extrinsic Fabry-Perot Interferometer) or FBG (Fiber Bragg Grating) sensors [9-12], etc. are used. A fiber-optic infrared spectroscopy-based cure monitoring is a method to estimate molecular structures by measuring infrared absorption spectrum of reactive molecules of resin. Although this technique is able to monitor progress of cure reaction in detail, it is difficult to measure cure index accurately due to large noise.

A refractive-index sensor, which is a technique to measure cure index of resin from Fresnel's reflection at interface between glass fiber and resin, is inexpensive due to simple optical system. Additionally, this sensor can measure both fast and slow cure reactions, and the measurement area, that is equivalent to beam diameter (typically 10 μm for a single-mode fiber), is very small. A refractive-index sensor has been proven to be applicable to monitor progress of cure reaction of resin from start to finish [8].

In the present paper, we applied refractive index sensors to measurement of cure index of GFRP laminates. Firstly, cure index measured by the sensors embedded along 0 and 90 direction of unidirectional laminates in order to investigate effect of reinforcements. Secondary, the sensors were employed to measure thickness-wise distribution of cure index of thick laminates. Finally, thermochemical model of cure reaction of the prepreg was obtained by a DSC analysis and the simulated results were compared with the experimental results.

2 PROCESS MONITORING METHODS

2.1 Estimation of degree-of-cure by refractive-index sensors

Figure 1 illustrates an optical fiber which is cut flat and embedded in resin. Light emitted from a light source transmits to the flat end in an optical fiber. At the end surface, some of light is reflected due to mismatch of refractive index between glass and resin. The reflected light returns to an optical power meter and the intensity is measured by it. In the present study, we pay attention to variation of refractive index. The optical intensity varies by ΔI when refractive index of resin does by Δn . The refractive index variation can be calculated by the following equations [8].

$$\Delta n = \frac{b_1 \left(a_1^2 b_2 (b_1 + b_2) + a_2^2 b_1^2 \nu \pm a_1 (b_1 + b_2) \sqrt{a_1^2 b_2^2 + a_2^2 b_1^2 \nu} \right)}{a_1^2 (b_1^2 - b_2^2) - a_2^2 b_1^2 \nu} \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} a_1 &= n_g + n_{air}, & a_2 &= n_g - n_{air}, \\ b_1 &= n_g + n_s, & b_2 &= n_g - n_s, & \nu &= \Delta I / I_{air} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Where, n_g is refractive index of an optical fiber, n_{air} is refractive index of the air which equals to 1.0 and I_{air} is optical intensity from the air as reference.

It is well known that refractive index of materials has temperature dependency. The temperature dependence curve shifts when cure reaction proceeds. Therefore, degree of cure of resin α can be estimated by removing temperature dependence from the obtained refractive index variation $\Delta n(\alpha, T)$ using the following formula.

$$\alpha = \frac{\Delta n(\alpha, T) - \Delta n(0, T_m) - \frac{dn}{dT}(0)(T - T_m)}{\Delta n(1, T_G) - \Delta n(0, T_m) + \frac{dn}{dT}(1)(T - T_G) - \frac{dn}{dT}(0)(T - T_m)} \quad (3)$$

Where, $dn/dT(\alpha)$ is temperature dependency of resin, which is a function of α . T_G is glass transition temperature of perfectly cured resin and T_m is temperature at starting of measurement.

Figure 1: Fresnel-based refractive-index measurement using an optical fiber

2.2 Simulation of cure index by DSC Analysis

A thermos-chemical model of cure reaction of the prepreg was experimentally obtained by DSC measurement. In the present paper, DOC was calculated by the following Kamal's model [13].

$$\dot{\alpha} = (k_1 + k_2 \alpha^m) \times (1 - \alpha)^n \quad (4)$$

$$k_1 = A_1 \exp\left(-\frac{E_1}{RT}\right), k_2 = A_2 \exp\left(-\frac{E_2}{RT}\right) \quad (5)$$

where R is gas constant, E_1 and E_2 are activation energies and m , n , A_1 and A_2 are material constants. These parameters were obtained by curve fitting the equation (4) to the experimental DOC curves measured by DSC as a function of temperature.

3 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

3.1 Process monitoring of unidirectional laminates by sensors embedded along 0 and 90 directions

Twelve sheets of GFRP prepreps (GE352G135SB Mitsubishi Rayon Co. Ltd.), which were 120 μ m thick, were stacked in the same direction on an aluminum flat plate. The fiber-optic sensors were embedded between middle prepreps of laminates. The laminate was heated from room temperature up to 140°C in 70 minutes and cured for 3 hours by a hot-press machine. When temperature reached 60°C, molding pressure of 0.5MPa was applied and held until the end of the molding.

Four sensors and a SLD light source were used for refractive index measurements as illustrated in Fig.3. The light from the source was divided into four optical paths by an optical switch. The intensity of reflected lights was measured by photo detectors (PD) individually. A thermocouple was also used for measuring temperature inside of laminates. All data from the sensors were recorded by a personal computer at 1 Hz. Location of optical fiber sensors were shown in Fig. 3. Two sensors were embedded in 0° direction of the laminate and the other sensors were embedded in 90° direction of the laminate in order to investigate effect of reinforcing fibers of laminates on cure index measurement of prepreg resin. This monitoring system was used for the other experiments in this paper.

3.2 DOC measurements of unidirectional laminates by DSC under monotonic heating conditions

Degree of cure of unidirectional laminates was measured by DSC under the monotonic heating conditions where the heating rates were 0.5, 1, 2, 3 and 5 K/min. In DSC measurement, 10 prepreps of 3 × 3 mm size were set in a sample pan and heated in nitrogen atmosphere. The molding pressure for the DSC measurement was zero in this experiment. From the heat flow data as function of temperature, relationship between DOC, rate of DOC and temperature was obtained for every heating rate.

3.3 Measurement of thickness-wise DOC distribution of laminates with non-uniform temperature distribution

Twelve sheets of GFRP prepreg were stacked in the same direction on an aluminum flat plate. Three optical fiber sensors were embedded between 1/2 layers, 10/11 layers and 19/20 layers of laminates as shown in Fig.4. In order to apply non-uniform temperature distribution in the thickness-wise direction, temperature programs shown in Fig.5 were applied to upper and lower heater plates of a hot-press machine. The upper plates heated from room temperature up to 140°C in 70 minutes and the lower plate, in 140 minutes.

Figure 2: Experimental set-up for process monitoring of GFRP laminates with multiple embedded optical fibers.

Figure 3: Specimen for process monitoring of GFRP laminates using fiber optic sensors embedded 0 and 90 degrees direction.

Figure 4: Sensor locations for measuring thickness-wise distribution of DOC of laminates.

Figure 5: Temperature programs of upper and bottom heating plates.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Process monitoring of laminates by sensors embedded along 0 and 90 directions

The resin was melted at about 100°C and then the sensor tip was fully covered with resin. Refractive index was calculated from the optical intensity using the equation (1) after melting of resin. Relationships between refractive index variation, temperature and molding time were plotted in Fig. 6. The first ordinate is refractive index variation Δn from the value at the end of cure process. From the figure, it was shown that the Δn curve of the sensor in FRP had large fluctuation from 25 to 50 minutes. This fluctuation is thought to be caused by the lights reflected from air voids. When the air voids exist very near the end surface of optical fiber, a transmitted light from the optical fiber scattered by the voids and some lights entered back into a core of the fiber and affected Fresnel's reflection light. The fluctuation disappeared after 50 minutes because large air voids disappeared near the sensor tip by vacuuming process.

The Δn tended to decrease linearly with temperature increase from 30 to 50 minutes. It is well known that this decrease is temperature dependency of refractive index. However, the Δn turned to increase but temperature was increasing after reached the minimum value. This reason was that proceeding of cure reaction increase refractive index. Therefore, it appeared that the prepregs used in this study began cure process at 110°C as soon as melted. The Δn curve almost converged at 70 minutes.

Figure 6: Relationships between refractive index variation, temperature and molding time obtained by sensors embedded in GFRP laminates along 0 and 90 directions.

From the Δn curves, DOC curves were calculated using the equation (3). Figure 7 shows relationship between cure index and curing time. From the figure, it was found that the DOC curves of 0° and 90° were very similar to each other. This means that effect of reinforcing fibers on measurement of cure index is very small. These results suggest that we can conduct quantitative measurement of cure index of FRP laminates by this method.

Figure 7: DOC (cure index) curves and temperature of GFRP laminates along 0 and 90 directions.

4.2 Process monitoring by DSC and fitting model

Figure 8 shows DOC curves obtained by DSC analysis and the simulation using the equation (4). The model parameters were obtained by fitting the Kamal model to the experimental data and tabulated in the Table 1. From the results, it appeared that the model agreed well with the experimental results when the heating rate is from 2 to 5 K/min. For the slow heating rate condition, the model should be improved.

Figure 8: Relationship between DOC and temperature for DSC measurement and simulation using Kamal model.

Table 1: Parameters of Kamal model of the prepreg ($k_1=1E-8$)

E_2 (kJ/mol)	A_2	m	n
76.616	99157600	0.766998	1.61233

4.3 Monitoring of thickness-wise distribution of DOC of laminates where thermal distribution occurs during molding

Figure 9 shows relationship between degree of cure, temperatures and curing time measured by the embedded fiber optic sensors (FOS) and thermocouples with the simulated DOC curves. The simulation results were calculated using the model obtained in the section 4.2 and the measured temperature profiles. The temperature curves shows that non-uniform thickness-wise distribution of temperature was applied to the laminates during molding. From the DOC curves measured by FOS, it was found that cure reaction of the top layer started and finished the fastest, and the bottom layer showed the slowest reaction behavior because the temperature of top layer was the highest. The simulated DOC curves were agreed well with the experimental curves at the positions of 1 and 2. However, the simulated results of the position 3 showed some difference from the experimental results. It is considered that the difference caused by inaccuracy of the model when the heating rate is slow. From these results, it appeared that the thickness-wise distribution of DOC of laminates could be measured successfully by the embedded multiple fiber-optic refractive-index sensors.

Figure 9: Measured and simulated DOC curves and temperature of GFRP laminates where non-uniform temperature distribution was applied.

It was difficult to figure out the starting time of cure reaction because very large fluctuation remained when cure index was about zero. Therefore, we investigated curing time and temperature when cure index is 0.5 or 0.9. The delays of middle and bottom layers from the top layer when $\alpha = 0.5$ are 12 and 34 minutes, respectively. These delays are considered to result from difference of heating rate. Since the temperatures of the top layer when $\alpha = 0.5$ and 0.9 are the highest among the three, it was found that cure reaction rate of the top layer is the fastest. It also appeared that the cure reaction of the bottom layer delayed by 39 minutes from the top when $\alpha = 0.9$. These information on delay of cure reaction is very important for searching optimal molding condition.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In the present paper, fiber-optic refractive-index sensors were employed for measurement of cure index of GFRP laminates. From the experimental results by the sensors embedded along 0 and 90 directions, it was found that reinforcements did not affect cure index measurement of laminates. From measurement and simulation of the thickness-wise distribution of DOC of laminates, it appeared that the thickness-wise distribution could be measured successfully by the embedded multiple fiber-optic refractive-index sensors.

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